

3D Visualization of a Cryptowallet's Seed phrase

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Abstract

Here is a proposal to encode and represent a *cryptocurrency wallet's seed phrase*¹ as a *scene* in *3D space*. This is *generative* and *steganographic* art which may be considered as an esthetic and intuitive way to apprehend the *space of possibilities* for a seed phrase (e.g. 2^{132} for a 12 words *seed phrase*).

1. Introduction to *seed phrase*

*BIP39*³ is a specification for encoding the *entropy*⁴ (from 128 to 256 bits) of a *cryptocurrency wallet* as a *seed phrase*. It is a sequence of between 12 and 24 words (respectively 128 and 256 bits for size of the entropy in binary). Each word is called a *mnemonic* and is chosen from the *BIP39 Dictionary* which contains 2048 words⁵. Thus each word corresponds to a slice of 11 bits ($2^{11}=2048$)

Note. 12 words require indeed 132 bits (12 words * 11 bits per word) so there are 4 missing bits (132 - 128) which are computed by a *checksum* as explained in *BIP39*.

1.1. From *seed phrase* to *3D scene*

BIP39 mnemonics was meant to be a more *human friendly* encoding representation than the *numeric encoding* (hexadecimal or base 58) of *entropy*.

e.g. « *hearn shallow deliver kitten excite reduce orange nasty blouse kiwi rival auto* »
is strictly equivalent (isomorphic) to *4558a0e83da4ed6826f499182f6eea87* (hexadecimal)

For the first *Homo sapiens* and our newborns as well, *Shapes* are (with other *stimuli* like color, sound, smell, etc...) the first representations of objects in the early stages of our cognitive / ethologic development⁶, this is why a *3D scene* could be more intuitive than a numeric (e.g. binary or hexadecimal) or even a sequence of words.

1.2. *Seed phrase* visualized as a scene in *3D space*

In the *seed phrase*, each mnemonic is indeed an index in the range 0..2047 of the *BIP39 dictionary*. This *word index* represented as a *binary number* is a 11 bits value ($2^{11} = 2048$).

These 11 bits can be arbitrarily divided in 3 parts, respectively:

- * 3 bits for X axis (value in the range [0..7]), let's call it «the orphan coordinate component» (see 1.2.2. Step 2)
- * 4 bits for Y and Z axes (value in the range [0..15])

1.2.1. *Cartesian coordinates*

For each *mnemonic* in the *Seed phrase*, get its *word index* value to extract the [x,y,z] coordinate, then:

- Step 1: X value is scaled to be in the same range than Y and Z (a value in the range [0..15])
- Step 2: [x,y,z] is used to set the position of the *mnemonic*, it is represented as a '*ball*' (a small sphere)
- Step 3: *Links* are drawn to represent the *mnemonic sequence*. The link is an *Arc* shape built from 3 points: 2 mnemonic shapes in the *seed phrase* (e.g. 1st and 2nd) and the *Centroid* (*geometric center* of all the mnemonic shapes).

1 Seed phrase: https://en.bitcoin.it/wiki/Seed_phrase

2 2^{132} is $5.5 * 10^{39}$ in base 10

3 *BIP39*: Mnemonic code for generating deterministic keys (<https://bips.dev/39/>)

4 *Entropy*: A random binary sequence which allows to generate the *key pair* for a *cryptocurrency wallet*. The *key pair* is a composed of the *public key* and the *private key*. The *public key* is used to generate the *wallet address* (to receive funds) while the *private key* allows to transferring part or totality of the funds to another *wallet address*.

5 *BIP39 dictionary* is *English* by default but other languages are available (eg. *French, German, Spanish, etc...*).
<https://github.com/bitcoin/bips/blob/master/bip-0039/bip-0039-wordlists.md>

6 Human Cognition of Geometric Shapes, A Window into the Mental Representation of Abstract Concepts (https://s-m.ac/documents/phd_thesis_mathias_sable-meyer.pdf)

1.2.2. Spherical and Cylindrical coordinates

NB: The following designs were inspired by Virus shapes (resp. *Coronavirus* and *Helical Virus*).

For each *mnemonic* in the Seed phrase, get its word index to extract the [x,y,z] coordinate:

- Step 1: Y and Z are used to position the *mnemonic shape* (an *Octahedron in Magenta color*) around the *Core shape* (a *Truncated Isocahedron* or a *Cylinder*).
- Step 2: X *'orphan coordinate component'* is used to display small rings which represent a 3 bits value in the range [0..7]. Each bit is represented as either a ring colored in *Magenta ('1')* or *Light grey ('0')*. The 3 rings are at the tip of a *'Stick'* which holds the *'Mnemonic shape'* (*Octahedron*), see animations here: <https://aladas.org/> and here: <https://opensea.io/collection/nft-3d-shaping-seed-words>.

2. Proof of Concept

We have developed a *Javascript* prototype with the help of *BabylonJS*⁷ (a 3D graphics library) which can export to *'glb'* format, thus it's possible to display the scene in a *'glb viewer'*⁸. The *'glb'* format allows to mint the scene as a *Non Fungible Token*. It's also possible to the scene export as *STL* for printing it in 3D .

3. Conclusion

This is only the *tip of the iceberg*, there is indeed a huge *'Design space'* to explore for this representation proposal. Even though this *visualization* is *steganographic by design* and atypical (at the time being), it could be used as an artistic way to display the *seed phrase* (e.g. as a 3D NFT or a 3D printed sculpture). Future enhancements of this representation could even be considered as a candidate alternative to the classic *QR code* encoding / representation because it's possible to develop a *dedicated reader* (to extract the *mnemonics* from the *'glb' 3D scene*).

⁷ *BabylonJS*: <https://www.babylonjs.com/>

⁸ *BabylonJS Sandbox*: <https://sandbox.babylonjs.com/>